

Predisposing factors influencing Myiasis: their treatment and control

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Abstract

Myiasis is the parasitic infestation of the living body with the larvae (maggots) of dipteran flies which grow inside the host while feeding on its tissue. The most common myiasis producing flies are botfly, blowfly, and screw worm fly. Myiasis varies widely, it may be facultative (Calliphorids) or obligatory (Oestrids) or cutaneous (*Lucillia* spp.), nasal (*Oestrus* spp.) or somatic (spp. *Hypoderma*). Predisposing factors of the myiasis are factors controlling the prevalence of the flies and factor determining the susceptibility of the host. Myiasis is a severe and persistent problem causing great economic losses for livestock industries worldwide, and also a moderately frequent disease for humans in rural tropical areas where myiasis producing flies are abundant, may require awareness to control of maggots producing flies and treatment for surgical removal of the parasites.

Keywords: Living animals, *Myiasis*, Predisposing factors, Treatment and Control

Introduction

Myiasis is the parasitic infestation of the body of living animal with the larvae (maggots) of dipteran flies which grow inside the host while feeding on its tissue. Although flies are mostly attracted to open wounds and soiled skin by urine and feces. The most common myiasis producing fly are botfly, blowfly, and screw worm fly which can create an infestation even on unbroken skin and have been known to use moist soil and non-myiasis flies (like housefly) as vector for their parasitic larvae.

Because some animals cannot react as effectively as humans to the causes and effects of myiasis, such infestations cause a severe and continuing problem for livestock industries

worldwide, causing severe economic losses where they are not diminished by human action (Otranto, Domenico., 2001). Although a greatest issue for animals, myiasis is also a relatively frequent disease for humans in rural tropical regions where myiatic flies succeed, and often may require medical attention for surgical removal of the parasites (John *et al.*, 2006).

Myiasis varies widely and such variations depend largely on the fly species and where the larvae are located. Some flies lay eggs in open wounds, other larvae may invade unbroken skin or enter the body through the nose or ears, and still others may be swallowed if the eggs are deposited on the lips or on food (John *et al.*, 2006). Myiasis is a greek word derived from “Myia” which means fly. It may be facultative as in Calliphorids or obligatory as in the Oestrids flies. It may be cutaneous (e.g. *Lucillia*), nasal (e.g. *Oestrus*) or somatic (e.g. *Hypoderma*).

1.

Myiasis classified on the basis of nature of the fly:

- **Obligatory myiasis:** Caused by the larvae of obligatory flies like *Oestrus*, *Hypoderma*, *Gasterophilus*, *Dermatobia*, *Cephalopsis* is called as obligatory myiasis. The part of the life cycle of these fly is completed in the host only.
- **Accidental myiasis:** Eggs on the larvae of the flies are ingested accidentally by the vertebrate host and **larvae produce myiasis in the gastrointestinal tract** e.g. **Muscid and Calliphorid flies** deposit their eggs on food stuff which will be consumed by the man and others accidentally.
- **Facultative myiasis:** Myiasis caused by the **larvae of facultative fly** is known as facultative myiasis, Larvae of the flies normally developed in decaying organic matter, faeces, sewage or decomposing vegetables, May also develop in the wound of live host e.g. *Lucilia*, *Calliphora* and *Sarcophaga*.

2. Myiasis classified on the basis the basis of affected body parts:

- **Intestinal myiasis:** When the invasion of egg and larvae occur in the intestinal tract then it is called intestinal myiasis. E.g. *Musca*, *Stomoxys* and *Sarcophaga spp.*

- **Gastric myiasis:** If the stomach is involved e.g. *Gastrophilus intestinalis*.
- **Nasal myiasis:** When the nasal passage is affected as found in *Oestrus ovis*.
- **Cutaneous myiasis:** When the invasion of skin is occurred eg. *Hypoderma* and *Dermatobia* spp.
- **Ophthalmomyiasis:** When eyes are involve e.g. *Rhinoestrus purpurensis* in man.
- **Auricular myiasis:** When invasion occur in ears e.g. *Chrysomya bezziana*.
- **Urinary myiasis:** If urinary tract is involved e.g. *Fannia canicularis* and *Musca domestica*.

3. Predisposing factors of the myiasis:

- **Factors controlling the prevalence of the flies** are humidity, temperature, abundance and suitability of food.
- **Factor determining the susceptibility of the host** are **presence of wound** on the body of the host, **soiling of wound** by the faeces or urine causes strike, **wrinkling of skin**, **presence of abscesses**, even **foul odour** of the animal also attract the fly, long **hair like wound** in sheep, **foot rot** may also cause to myiasis, **flock size** and **stocking density** may predispose the risk of myiasis and **frequent raining** also increases the susceptibility of the host.

4. Treatment : The treatment of myiasis is based on the mechanical removal of larvae without breaking them, blocking the respiration (occlusion) of the larva, and using larvicidal antiparasitics used for killing the possible existing larvae and to discontinued further myiasis. This needs anesthetizing the animals and clipping the hair around the area for better visibility and healing. Cleaning the area and removing necrotic tissue will improve the healing process. Secondary bacterial infections are very common, so a proper wound management is advised to the owner and antibiotics administered if necessary.

- **Refoxanide** can be used orally @ 10 mg/kg b.wt.
- **Closantel** @ 10 mg/kg should be repeated after 8 weeks to eliminate 98% larvae.
- **Ivermectin** @ 0.2 mg/kg b. wt. subcutaneously.
- **Trichlorphon** is also effective when used by aerosol technique.

5. Control : To ensure prevention, environmental conditions of the animals should be clean and dry, and also use the flies screen, proper dressing of wounds, regular shearing of wools and prophylactic treatment should be given.

- Use of insect growth regulator such as **juvenile hormone produced by *Corpora allata* in insects** and **Chitin synthesis inhibitor** like **benzoyl phenyl urea, cyromazine** which affect the metamorphosis, moulting, exoskeleton formation and development of insects.
- **Mechanical control** by mechanical removal of larvae from affected site.
- **Biological control** by use of entomopathogenic fungi like *Tolypocladium niveum* spores to adult *Oestrus ovis* causes 100 % mortality. Some **phoretic mites** also reduced insemination rate.
- **Sterile insect technique:** Release of **irradiated sterile males** into a wild population to mate with fertile female which produces **eggs that do not hatch**. This technique has been used very successfully against the **screw worm fly, *Cochliomyia hominivorax***.
- **Genetic control by Genetic translocation of Y chromosome** by the exposure to radiation. It may give partial sterility in **male *Lucilia cuprina***.
- **Immunological control** by a protective antigen, **PM44** has been identified from the peritrophic membrane of the larval gut of ***Lucilia cuprina* has shown 60 % decrease in larval growth**.

Conclusion

Myiasis is a severe and persistent problem causing great economic losses to livestock industries worldwide, and also a moderately frequent disease for humans in rural tropical areas where myiatic flies are abundant may require awareness to control of maggots producing flies and treatment for surgical removal of the parasites. As myiasis causes considerable damage in livestock animals, control of parasitic flies is attempted where raising of sheep, goats, cows, or horses represents a substantial economic activity.

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